

Exploring Sequential Code Embeddings for Predicting Student Success in an Introductory Programming Course

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ABSTRACT

Methods to encode high-dimensional features into dense vectors or “embeddings” have gained attention in educational data mining to transform large state data spaces into condensed representations suitable as input to machine learning algorithms. One such technique is *Code2Vec*, an embedding technique developed by software engineers to predict method names for snippets of code written by expert programmers. In this paper, we have adapted *Code2Vec* to embed student programs and extended it to create embeddings for sequences of student responses using a long short-term memory (LSTM) network. Using these submission sequence embeddings, we successfully predicted student exam grades in the 2021 CSEDM data challenge dataset. Regression models trained on *Code2Vec* vectors and our sequential embeddings achieved comparable results to the winners of the data challenge. Further, our sequential embedding technique slightly but significantly outperformed the technique of prediction using students’ best assignment submissions. This suggests that examining the totality of students’ work can yield important information about students’ internal knowledge states. The promising results obtained from incorporating students’ sequence of submissions support further research in incorporating sequential modeling for accurate student modeling and developing effective adaptive support.

Keywords

student performance modeling, code embedding, sequential analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

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Recent years have seen a surge in students’ interest in introductory programming courses. At the same time, the challenging nature of these courses results in high rates of failure and dropout. Automated early prediction of students’ performance can help address this challenge by providing an opportunity for timely intervention by educators [11, 23]. One way to achieve this goal is to analyze students’ programming submissions to model their state of knowledge and, on this basis, predict their performance. A significant challenge of this task is identifying features that capture the essential semantic and structural information within students’ programs [9, 22, 13]. Furthermore, the massive variety in possible submissions by students creates a sparse state-space negatively affecting the training process of machine learning approaches [17].

Embedding techniques are emerging approaches that transform large state spaces into condensed representations suitable as input to machine learning algorithms. Following the success of embedding approaches in natural language processing, an area that also suffers from dealing with vast state-spaces, efforts for adapting this approach for programming analysis are gaining momentum [27]. We argue that by utilizing embedding techniques, we can reduce the high-dimensional state space of programming submissions into lower-dimension vectors that can capture the essence of structural and semantic information represented by programs.

This paper adapts *Code2Vec* [2], a state-of-the-art embedding model initially designed for embedding professional programs, to the CSEDM 2021 data challenge dataset collected from students’ interactions with *CodeWorkout* [4], a system that offers coding exercises for introductory programming courses. We further explored an approach for aggregating students’ consecutive submissions to programming challenges using deep learning to identify effective methods for capturing students’ learning progress. The program embeddings were used in temporal and atemporal machine learning approaches to predict students’ performance as measured by their final exam grades in the semester.

Our results demonstrated that the *Code2Vec* method yields vectors that are useful for student modeling and that our sequential embedding technique yields significantly better results. In this paper, we explore various approaches for

representing student programs and conducting effective student modeling. We then discuss promising directions for improving upon the current models and potential areas for exploration.

2. RELATED WORK

Our work draws from the CS education and software engineering fields, both of which have been striving to develop effective methods of program representation for machine learning. By integrating software engineering techniques for program representation into student modeling, we hope to draw benefit from both approaches.

2.1 Program Representation

A significant challenge posed by programming analysis is identifying features that capture important semantic and structural information from students’ programs. Many related works utilize the abstract syntax trees (ASTs) generated from students’ programming assignments directly to conduct their analysis. For example, [19] provides automated hints utilizing the contextual tree decomposition algorithm and the AST representation of students’ submitted programming solutions. Other approaches have tried to decompose the ASTs into feature sets to be used in standard machine learning algorithms. For instance, Hosseini et al. [8] use an ontological-based java parser to represent a program with its encompassing concepts. Jamil [10] used CDG: Hierarchical concept structure to capture programming patterns from pattern graphs to classify similarities of programs. Given the vast state space of students’ submitted solutions, most proposed feature extraction techniques can work with small-scale problems and fail to represent larger-scale problems.

Representation Learning is another approach for feature extraction that refers to the use of ML techniques to extract meaningful information from low-level, raw data [25]. An emerging and promising approach is the utilization of code embeddings for representing important conceptual and structural information in programs. Embedding approaches have long been successfully used in Natural Language Processing [5, 24] and other fields such as graph and network analysis [7] and image processing [26] to capture different structural data more efficiently. A state-of-the-art code embedding model, Code2Vec, was introduced in [2]. This model leverages crucial paths in ASTs, referred to as “path contexts”, to automatically identify method names for programs written by professional software engineers. In [17], an embedding process was introduced to convert Abstract Syntax Tree (AST) representation of student programs into embedded vectors and was used to predict students’ next possible step to the correct solution.

2.2 Predicting Student Success

Research on predicting students success using logs of their interaction with online learning systems emerged as one of the most popular applications of educational data mining [23, 21]. Early automated prediction of student success and failure in large introductory programming courses is essential to improving students’ retention. Many efforts are taking place to predict students’ performance early on to enable

Table 1: Dataset description

Students	773
Submissions	162158
Compilable submissions	62757
Correct submissions	21546
Incorrect submissions	41211

timely and impactful intervention to support struggling students who are predicted to fail or drop out. In [6], the final programming performance of students was predicted using first programming assignments in block-based programming languages using χ^2 differential sequence mining. In another study [15], students’ online programming data was used for a summative analysis of students’ final grades in a course. The correctness of the programs was used in calculating likelihood and measuring a ranking for the grades obtained from students’ ability measurement using Item Response Theory (IRT). In another study [13], students’ program correctness were predicted using an ASTNN model [27] where code embeddings were learned at the statement level from ASTs of programming submissions. They also predicted students’ early success using a Temporal-ASTNN model that used an LSTM model to for its prediction task.

In this work, we explore different approaches to embed students’ programs into feature vectors. We further investigate the effectiveness of our embedded vectors by incorporating them in various machine learning approaches to predict students’ performance at the end of the course.

3. DATASET

In this study, we utilized students program submissions data collected from CodeWorkout¹, an online system for practicing Java programming. CodeWorkout enables student to learn programming concepts by solving programming problems and submitting them to the system to be graded. The programming problems require students to write one or more Java methods focused on basic programming concepts including arithmetic operations, data types, strings, arrays, conditionals, and loops. Students can submit multiple solutions to the same problem.

We used the publicly-available CodeWorkout dataset² collected from Spring 2019 and Fall 2019, which is in ProgSnap2 format [20]. Only the compilable programs were kept in order to eliminate programs which were not parsable into ASTs. We incorporated students’ solutions to 30 distinct problems. The dataset includes students’ code submissions, scores of individual submissions as well as their final exam grades for the semester, grades and scores ranging from 0 to 1. The dataset was already divided into training and test data; however, the labels for the test data were hidden in order to accurately calculate model scores for submissions to the CSEDM data competition. Therefore, we only performed our analysis using the training portion of the dataset. Table 1 briefly describes the characteristics of the dataset.

¹<https://CodeWorkOut.cs.vt.edu/>

²<https://pslclatashop.web.cmu.edu/Files?datasetId=3458>

4. METHODOLOGY

We modeled student performance by extracting features from programming submissions using Code2Vec code embeddings. Code2Vec is a neural model which predicts Java method names. Code embeddings can be generated by extracting the model’s internal state after making a prediction. [2] We trained three distinct Code2Vec models to generate vector embeddings of students’ programming data. We will refer to these models as ”from-scratch,” ”pre-trained,” and ”further-trained.” The new model is a Code2Vec model trained only on the programs in the CodeWorkout dataset. The pre-trained model was downloaded from the Code2Vec Github page³ and was trained on a large dataset containing about 16 million Java methods. The further trained model is an instance of the pre-trained model further trained on the CodeWorkout Java methods.

This paper introduces a method of programming submission embedding which further utilizes these Code2Vec vectors. In the CodeWorkout dataset, each programming assignment allowed for arbitrarily many submissions. We hypothesized that utilizing multiple submissions for each assignment would improve accuracy when predicting future student behavior. This hypothesis was tested by creating embeddings using these submissions using an LSTM network. There have been a number of recent works using LSTMs for constructing vector representations of data [14, 18, 16]. We evaluated this LSTM embedding technique against selecting the Code2Vec embedding for the highest-scoring submission for the problem. We combined these Code2Vec embeddings with other features from students’ assignment attempts in order to predict their final grades.

4.1 Code Embedding with Code2Vec

We used Code2Vec to generate code embeddings for our analysis. Code2Vec is a neural model which predicts the names of Java methods by creating an embedding of each method’s AST. To create code embeddings, Code2Vec breaks an AST into ”path contexts”. Each path context consists of two leaf nodes (generally corresponding tokens in the program) and the set of nodes connecting them through their closest common ancestor in the AST (henceforth referred to as the path). Figure 1 shows an example of a path context. During training, Code2Vec compiles a vocabulary of paths (P) and a vocabulary of leaves (L). The model trains two embedding matrices of size $|P| \times e$ and $|L| \times e$ to embed each of the elements in P and L respectively, where e is a model hyperparameter indicating the length of the embeddings.

Path context embeddings are created by concatenating the embeddings for the leaves (l_1 and l_2) and the embedding for the path (p) and then passing $l_1 p l_2$ through a fully-connected neural network layer. After this is done for each path context, a code vector is created by taking a weighted sum of each path context vector, v_n (equation 1).

$$c = \sum_{n=1}^m (a \cdot v_n) v_n \quad (1)$$

where m is the number of path contexts and a is an attention vector of size $3e$, trained by the model. After being calcu-

³<https://github.com/tech-srl/code2vec>

Figure 1: An example path context, highlighted in red.

Figure 2: Architecture of Code2Vec model.

lated, these code vectors can be extracted from the model and used as input for other machine learning tasks. Figure 2 illustrates the architecture of Code2Vec model.

4.2 Vector Generation for CSEDM Data

To generate vectors for the CSEDM challenge dataset, we downloaded a pre-trained Code2Vec model available on the Code2Vec Github page and further trained it to predict the method names of the CodeWorkout submissions. We hypothesized that the pre-trained model might have learned general features about the Java code which would allow it to better represent the CodeWorkout submissions; on the other hand, further training the model on the CodeWorkout dataset might help adapting the embedding matrix to the special characteristics unique to this dataset. To test our hypothesis we trained and used three distinct models as follows:

- New Code2Vec: the Code2Vec model trained only on the methods in the CodeWorkout dataset from scratch.
- Pre-trained Code2Vec: the pre-trained model by the Code2Vec authors on 16 million Java methods.⁴
- Further-trained Code2Vec: the pre-trained model, further trained on the CodeWorkout dataset.

⁴<https://github.com/tech-srl/code2vec>

These models were used to generate code vectors for every student submission in the dataset. Most submissions were comprised of only one method; however, some contained multiple methods. Because Code2Vec creates a vector for each method in the program it predicts, these submissions yielded more than one vector. In order to represent each submission with a single vector, these submissions were represented as the sum of the code vectors for each of their methods. This improved model performance over only including the vector for the first method in the submission.

4.2.1 Sequential Encoding of Students’ Problem Attempts

The training set consisted of thirty problems, each of which permitted unlimited student submissions. We used two strategies for representing students’ attempts at each problem: best submission and sequential problem embedding, explained below. We included four features along with the embedding associated with each problem. These were the average score among submissions, the best score, the number of submissions, and the assignment number (0-29). For the LSTM, each problem was associated with a corresponding time step for each student, (i.e. the input tensor for the LSTM was of size [Number of Students, Number of Problems (30), $(3e + 4)$]. For the other regression models, each vector of features was concatenated and then reduced using principal component analysis (PCA). The input matrix for these problems was of size [Number of Students, Number of Problems (30) * $(3e + 4)$].

Best Submissions: A student’s “best” submission for a problem was considered to be the submission for which they had the highest score based on unit tests. For submissions that had the same score, we picked the latest submission. This best submission was represented as the Code2Vec vector for the submitted program.

Sequential Problem Embedding: We also used an LSTM to aggregate all of a students’ submissions for a single problem into a single vector. Figure 3 shows our method for embedding these submissions. We selected two descriptive statistics, the highest score among the submissions and the average score, and trained this problem embedding LSTM to predict them using the Code2Vec vector for each submission. Since there were a variable number of submissions for each student-problem pair, we truncated or padded all of the vectors for each submission to 30. 30 was chosen because, for the training dataset, 99% of student-assignment pairs had 30 or fewer submissions. For problem-student pairs where students made fewer than 30 submissions, the tensor containing the time series for their submission was pre-padded with zero vectors. For problem-student pairs where students exceeded than 30 submissions, all but the last 30 submissions were truncated.

We tuned the hyperparameters for our LSTM using HyperBand tuning [12] to find the number of hidden layers, number of hidden neurons, and the alpha value for leaky ReLU. The number of LSTM units, and therefore, the length of our embedding vectors, was fixed at 256.

HyperBand is a hyperparameter tuning algorithm which selects configurations of hyperparameters by running several

Figure 3: The LSTM model used to embed each problem.

selection iterations. It relies on the assumption that the optimal configuration will outperform other configurations even when the model is trained with fewer epochs. Each iteration, it compares many configurations for a few training epochs and selects the best-performing configurations, which are tested in the next iteration. Doing this pruning greatly reduces the time needed to perform hyperparameter optimization over other methods.

We trained the models mentioned in section 4.1 and extracted vectors for each student-problem pair by taking the internal state from the LSTM after predicting the average and best scores for the submissions.

4.3 Predicting Learning Outcomes

In order to analyze statistical significance in differences in model performance, evaluated each model using 10-fold cross-validation as described in [3]. After obtaining the results, we calculated significance using the Student’s t-test and the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. Hyper-parameters were tuned using 5-fold cross-validation within one of the 10 training folds.

We trained several regression models: linear regression, lasso regression, Gaussian Process Regression, and an LSTM to predict students’ final exam grades based on their programming submissions. Below, we discuss these models, their training processes, and different approaches we have taken to encode students’ submissions to be utilized for the prediction task. We compared the performance of these models against a naive baseline method: predicting the mean of the training data. For our non-sequential regression models, instead of representing the data for each problem as a separate time step, we concatenated all of the Code2Vec vectors for each of the 30 problems and reduced their features using principal component analysis (PCA). Along with each Code2Vec vector, we embedded four extra features: the individual submission grade, the best submission grade, the number of submissions, and the problem number.

4.3.1 Mean Final Exam Grade

Our baseline method is to predict the mean final exam grade from the training data for every student. We chose this as a baseline to evaluate how well our models performed against the most naive prediction task possible.

4.3.2 Linear Regression

Linear regression is a simple regression technique that assumes a linear relation between the input features and the projected results.

Figure 4: Diagram of an LSTM. Circled components are neural layers, squared components are operations.

4.3.3 Lasso Regression

Lasso regression uses a penalty term in order to avoid overfitting. We chose lasso regression over ridge regression because lasso can reduce weights to absolute zero. We tuned the lasso regression model to determine the best value of α , the penalty coefficient, from the set $[1e-10, 1e-8, 1e-6, 1e-4, 1e-2, 0.1, 1, 2, 5]$. The results of a 5-fold cross validation approach resulted in $1e-2$ as the best value for α .

4.3.4 Gaussian Process Regression

We chose Gaussian process regression since our dataset is small, has high number of features, and is noisy. Utilizing a 5-Fold cross validation for hyper-parameter tuning we set the kernel to be RBF, length scale to 10 from the set of $[0.5, 1, 10]$, and noise level to 5 from the set of $[0.5, 1, 5]$.

4.3.5 The LSTM Model

An LSTM is a recurrent neural network which makes predictions on time series data. The LSTM takes in new data from the input for every time step and propagates input from previous time steps. At every step, there are three inputs: two from the previous time step (C_{t-1}, h_{t-1}) and one from the data (x_t). Every step also has two outputs: C_t and h_t . C_t represents information that the LSTM will “remember” from previous states and helps preserve information over a long series of time steps. h_t represents the output for the LSTM layer.

The LSTM contains a number of internal layers. Three significant layers are the “gates,” neural layers whose output is run through the logistic sigmoid function. The gates serve to block or allow information through the LSTM. The first gate, the “forget gate” is calculated as f_t in equation 2 where W_f are the weights for the forget gate and b_f is the bias term for the forget gate. The output of the forget gate is multiplied with C_{t-1} . A value of zero will reset C_{t-1} , causing it to “forget” the value from the previous iteration.

$$f_t = \sigma(W_f \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_f) \quad (2)$$

The second gate, the “input gate,” updates the state of the LSTM to incorporate new information from the input. i_t (Equation 3) controls how much new information is included and \tilde{C}_t (Equation 4) is the new information.

$$i_t = \sigma(W_i \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_i) \quad (3)$$

$$\tilde{C}_t = \tanh(W_C \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_C) \quad (4)$$

The internal state of the model is updated according to equation 5.

$$C_t = f_t * C_{t-1} + i_t * \tilde{C}_t \quad (5)$$

The last gate filters the output of the LSTM according to equations 6 and 7

$$o_t = \sigma(W_o \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_o) \quad (6)$$

$$h_t = o_t * \tanh(C_t) \quad (7)$$

Figure 5 shows the LSTM model we trained to predict students’ final exam grades. The number of hidden layers, the number of neurons in the layers, the number of LSTM units, and the alpha values for the leaky ReLU were all tuned using HyperBand.

Figure 5: The LSTM model used to predict the final exam grade.

5. RESULTS

To evaluate the effectiveness of our models, we calculated the root-mean-square error (RMSE) of our predicted exam grades with regard to the actual exam grades. RMSE was chosen partly because MSE was the metric by which the CSEDM competition was judged. Furthermore, since RMSE uses the same units as the dependant variable (student grades from 0-1) it is representative of how far our grade estimations are from the actual value. Finally, RMSE penalizes large errors which makes it a suitable measurement for the purpose of predicting grades, where models that have a consistent level of accuracy are more useful than models which are more erratic.

Apart from the LSTM, we implemented linear, lasso and Gaussian process regression. Each of these models was also evaluated using 10-fold cross-validation and trained using vectors from all 3 Code2Vec models. We evaluated these models using R^2 along with RMSE. R^2 indicates the proportion of variation explained by independent variables in a regression model for dependent variables.

Tables 2 and 3 show the results for all of our regression models trained on the Code2Vec embeddings for the best submission and the sequential problem embeddings respectively. Every combination of models was trained using embeddings from each of the three Code2Vec models but only the best model from each Code2Vec model is shown. These values are averaged from the 10 values obtained by performing 10-fold cross-validation. Standard deviations are shown in parentheses and the best-performing model in each table is shown in bold.

Table 2: Exam Grade Prediction Performance (Best Submission)

Models	Code Embeddings	RMSE	R ²
MFEG	–	0.247 (0.020)	-0.010 (0.018)
Linear	Pre-trained	0.269 (0.042)	-0.218 (0.296)
Lasso	Further-Trained	0.212 (0.026)	0.251 (0.109)
GPR	Pre-Trained	0.206 (0.024)	0.290 (0.100)
LSTM	Pre-Trained	0.237 (0.026)	0.056 (0.178)

Table 3: Exam Grade Prediction Performance (Sequential Problem Embedding)

Models	Code Embeddings	RMSE	R ²
MFEG	–	0.247 (0.020)	-0.010 (0.018)
Linear	Pre-Trained	0.239 (0.027)	0.0354 (0.214)
Lasso	Pre-Trained	0.206 (0.025)	0.292 (0.108)
GPR	Pre-Trained	0.204 (0.024)	0.309 (0.0942)
LSTM	Pre-Trained	0.232 (0.025)	0.095 (0.168)

5.1 Statistical Tests

The performance of every model shown in Tables 2 and 3 was compared with every other model using both the Student’s T-test and the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. Using a significance threshold of $p \leq 0.05$, both tests indicate significance for the same set of models. Most pairs of models fall within our chosen threshold for significance. Some models do not show statistically significant improvement over the mean final grade prediction. Namely (p-values reported from the Wilcoxon signed-rank test):

- Lasso regression predicting with the best submission (p=0.13)
- Linear regression predicting with sequential problem embedding (p=0.92)
- Lasso regression predicting with sequential problem embedding (p=0.55)
- Gaussian process regression predicting with sequential problem embedding (p=0.08)

Despite this, every model trained using sequential problem embedding significantly outperforms its counterpart trained on best submission.

6. DISCUSSION

In the following section, we discuss our results, the shortcomings of our approach, opportunities for growth, and future directions of work.

This paper investigated a variety of approaches for representing students’ programming submissions using Code2Vec embeddings. It further evaluated the embedded vectors by utilizing them in a variety of regression models to predict students’ performance on a final exam. We used three distinct approaches to generate Code2Vec embeddings: training a model from scratch on our dataset, using a model pre-trained on a large dataset, and further training such a model on our dataset.

We further explored two ways to represent student performance for a single problem. “Best submission” used the embedding from students’ best submission only and “sequential problem embedding” used an LSTM to aggregate all of a students’ submissions into a single vector. The best results across all models were obtained by utilizing the pre-trained Code2Vec model on the sequential embedding of students’ programs. We did not predict this to be the case. We hypothesized that further training the pre-trained model would adapt it to our specific concept while taking advantage of deep structural information on programming data learned during its prior training. Our results indicate that the deep structural information is beneficial to student modeling but the further training in our dataset adds noise or confusion. Further training of Code2Vec could eliminate the ability to make certain distinctions between submissions to the same problem, by associated all such submissions with the same method name. This would indicate to the model that these submissions have the same functionality when, in reality, they may not, being created by novice programming students.

Furthermore, we believe that utilizing the sequence of students’ submissions as opposed to one single submission can provide more information about students’ learning. However, utilizing every single submission might add noise to the system because of student actions that aren’t indicative of learning, for example, gaming the system. Thus, in the future, we plan to utilize features such as time between submissions, and code difference between submissions to filter out the most significant submissions for our task.

We introduced a method of sequential modeling across programming submissions for the purpose of feature extraction. Because this sequential problem embedding technique only requires information about students’ programming submissions and the associated grades, an embedding model can be further adapted to students in future semesters before they receive their final grades. The fact that this sequential problem embedding method yielded better results than our naive method of assignment representation using the best submission indicates two things: first, sequential problem embedding more accurately captures student knowledge state than the non-sequential approach. Secondly, and more generally, high-level student modeling tasks such as predicting final exam scores can be improved upon using the results of low-level student modeling tasks, such as predicting a student’s submission grades on an individual assignment.

Most of models were able to achieve statistically significant, but minor improvement over the mean grade prediction baseline. We believe our mixed significance results are due to a small n for the statistical tests as well as the distribution of the grades in the dataset. 65% of final grades fell within 20% of the mean final grade. The lasso and Gaussian process regression models outperforming our LSTM models suggests that we did not have enough data for deep learning. Gaussian Process regression being the best-performing model is likely due to the benefits GPR yields when the number of samples is small and the number of features is large [28], as was the case in this analysis. Further, predicting student success using the noisy data of their programs is a difficult task. In the future work section, we propose some methods for tackling these challenges.

Using these methods of feature extraction for novice programmers can help give insight into their learning process and assist in the development of automated learning tools. By expanding on these methods to investigate which features Code2Vec and sequential problem embedding encode, we can design tools that utilize this information to accurately track students' knowledge states. Furthermore, we can use this knowledge to create tools such as automated tutors and interventions for struggling students.

7. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we introduced a novel sequential program embedding for predicting students' future performance. We presented the results from training and utilizing three distinct code embedding approaches. We further explored various ways to represent sequences of programming submissions (i.e. best submission, and sequential problem embedding). Our results demonstrated that a pre-trained Code2Vec model can achieve the best results by utilizing sequential problem embeddings. Further, our explorations have provided a way towards modeling student knowledge states from sequential programming submissions.

8. FUTURE WORK

8.1 Improving the Code Embedding Approach

Over the course of our work, we identified multiple ways to improve the code embedding process. First, the embeddings generated by the Code2Vec model are very dependent on the values of the leaves in the AST including the names of variables. This is detrimental to modeling student code because students often use non-descriptive variable names. In the future, we plan to compare our approach to a modified version of the Code2Vec model that ignores method names in order to better accommodate the programming habits of novice programmers. Furthermore, we will make use of improvements to the model found in its successor, Code2Seq [1], which models path contexts as sequences using a bi-directional LSTM. By utilizing this method, we can reduce memory usage in the model and encode path contexts not present in the training set.

8.2 Knowledge Component Extraction

Code2Vec creates its vectors by embedding and aggregating paths through the AST. Because the resulting vectors are capturing important information about the structure of

the programs, we hypothesize that these paths may serve as useful substitutes for knowledge components (KCs). By automatically extracting the most important paths identified by the attention model and treating them as pseudo-KCs, that can be utilized for student modeling purposes. Automated KC extraction for programs eliminates the need for experts to manually label problems with their encompassing KCs. Furthermore, extracting information about students' knowledge from their submissions enables us to assess students' submission, reducing the need for rigorous, problem-specific unit testing development.

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